

D1.8 Dissemination and Communication Campaign

WP1 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

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PROJECT DETAILS AND DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

PROJECT DETAILS

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

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SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
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0.4	27.03.2025	Franco Cacialli	Internal Review
0.5	31.03.2025	Elena Bellotti	Third Release
1.0	31.03.2025	Giuseppe Barillaro	Final Release

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PROJECT DETAILS AND DELIVERABLE INFORMATION	2
DOCUMENT HISTORY	3
GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS	5
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2. COMMUNICATION MONITORING & CONTROL	7
3. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS.....	8
3.1 X account.....	8
3.2 Instagram account.	9
3.3 RESORB’s website	10
3.4 RESORB’s Gmail Account	11
3.5 Communication with cancer patient associations	11
3.6 Participation to national/international conferences.....	16
3.7 Press and Web News Release	21
3.8 Participation to popular science events	22
3.9 Papers on International Journals.....	22
3.10 Patents	23
3.11 Collaborations with industries.....	24
4. BIBLIOGRAPHY/REFERENCES	24

GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Extended Definition
CD	Communication Descriptor
DCC	Dissemination and Communication Campaign
KVI	Key Value Indicator
UNIFI	Università di Pisa

DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed in this Deliverable are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the deliverable D1.8 Dissemination and Communication Campaign (DCC) is to detail, monitor, and refine the implementation of the RESORB's dissemination and communication plan [1]. In particular, the DCC identifies the tools we have exploited for sharing the RESORB vision and results with the targeted audiences. Moreover, this document identifies indicators of the effectiveness of our dissemination and communication campaigns. Such indicators will give us appropriate feedbacks to improve and/or adjust our communication actions.

The implementation of the dissemination and communication campaigns is fully integrated into RESORB through the WP1 led by UNIFI. However, all the consortium members have been involved in the implementation and monitoring of the communication campaign. In this regard, the DCC can be considered as a living document, which will be updated as soon as any action of the communication campaign is implemented and/or changed. All the RESORB partners will contribute to the updating of the DCC and will receive a copy of the amended DCC.

2. COMMUNICATION MONITORING & CONTROL

A key point of the RESORB communication plan and strategy is generating an optimal flow of information between the RESORB "universe" and possible stakeholders at any moment in time. In this regard, it is essential to monitor and control the RESORB communication and to assess the information both flow and impact with respect to the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan [1]. To this end, we identified the following communication descriptors (CDs) and key value indicators (KVI):

Communication Descriptors:

- Author(s) and Contributor(s) of any action (source: RESORB partners)
- Type of the action (source: RESORB partners);
- Flow direction, namely, one-way exchange such as website and press release or two-way exchange such as exhibition, school visit (source: RESORB partners);
- Main recipients (source: RESORB partners and analytical tools)
- Date of the monitoring process (source: RESORB partners and analytical tools)
- Place of the action, such as webpage, conference site (source: RESORB partners)
- Content of the action (e.g., posts, press release, (source: RESORB partners)

Key value indicators (i.e., size and/or impact of the action):

- Number of visitors, downloads, documents, events on the RESORB project website (source: Google Search Console)
- Number of followers, followings, reads, likes, and posts on the social media (source: X-, ResearchGate-, LinkedIn-own statistics)
- Number of stakeholders reached (source: RESORB partners),

- Number of external events with participation of the consortium partners (source: RESORB partners)
- Number of participants in RESORB-own events (source: participants list)

The outcomes of the monitoring process will be used to timely adjust the communication campaign and meet the goals of the communication plan, or to change and improve this latter. After making changes to the communication campaign, we will frequently monitor their effect through DCs and KVIs to determine the result of the modifications we made. This loop between 1) campaign, 2) monitor, and 3) control will allow reaching the largest number of target stakeholders, thus, extending the impact of RESORB beyond its lifecycle.

3. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

To implement the communication plan we used various tools/channels with their own specificity, which depends on several aspects including the targeted audience (i.e., general vs. specialized) or the way to communicate (i.e., one-way exchange vs. two-way exchange).

3.1 X account.

The X account of RESORB, after its birth in May 2022, has started collecting followers and informing a broad audience (e.g., oncologists, citizens, and research labs) about the project aims, status, and achievements.

The RESORB X account has the following DCs and KVIs:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size
UNIPI	Social media	One-way	1. Civic society 2. Research community	21/02/2025	https://x.com/resorb_project	Posts	Followings = 103 Followers = 47 Post = 26 Likes = 54 Repost = 12

3.2 Instagram account.

A RESORB's Instagram account was created on September 30th 2022 to inform the general public, but also the scientific community and industrial professionals, about the project aims, status, and achievements.

RESORB

19
post

89
follower

148
seguiti

Bioresorbable OptoElectronic System for In-Vivo and In-Situ Monitoring of Chemotherapeutic Drugs - an EIC PathFinder Open project funded by the EC

The RESORB Instagram account has the following DCs and KVIs:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size
UNIPI	Social media	One-way	1. Civic society 2. Research community	18/02/2025	https://www.instagram.com/resorbproject/?igsh=cjAyMHkwNWwxdD14&utm_source=qr#	Posts	Followings = 148 Followers = 89 Posts = 19 Likes = 250 Reached accounts = 813 (last 90 days) Visualization = 1722 (last 90 days)

3.3 RESORB's website

The website of the project, lunched on May 27th 2022, has informed the civic society about the RESORB vision and impacts through the content of the Home, Project, and News&Events pages, as well as specialized audience by posting job opportunities, new entries and recent publications in the Publications and Partners pages.

The main DCs and KVs of the project website are:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size (last 16 months)
RESORB partners	Web content	One-way	1. Civic society 2. Research community	24/02/2025	https://www.resorb-project.eu	RESORB at glance, Consortium composition, News & Events, Publications,	Total Clicks = 204 Total impressions = 12037

A screenshot of Google Search Console indexing the project website is shown here below.

3.4 RESORB's Gmail Account

RESORB has a Gmail account (i.e., resorbproject@gmail.com) that allows us to communicate directly with RESORB's subscribers and inform them about the status of the project, its outcomes, and related events.

3.5 Communication with cancer patient associations

To raise awareness about the RESORB technology and assess acceptance in view of possible technology transfer from lab to market, we prepared an anonymous questionnaire specifically tailored to target groups we want to reach. The questionnaire was presented to 104 cancer patients at the Santa Chiara Hospital in Pisa. The questionnaire is below reported.

Anonymous Questionnaire		
Patient description		
1. What is your sex?		
	Male	
	Female	
	Intersex	
	Prefer not to answer	
2. What is your age?		
	<45 years old	
	45-60 years old	
	> 60 years old	
	Prefer not to answer	
3. Which of the following job family best describes your current professional occupation?		
Health Services		Professionals
Education		Others
4. Are you currently taking anticancer drugs?		
	Yes	

	No	
	Prefer not to answer	
(If you answered yes to the previous question) How long have you been taking anticancer drugs?		
	<2 months	
	2-4 months	
	>4 months	
	Prefer not to answer	

Patient awareness about implantable and bioresorbable technologies			
1. Are you aware of the existence of implantable biomedical devices?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
2. Do you have any biomedical implants in your body (e.g., a pacemaker, a PICC line, or Port central vascular catheter)?			
	YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO
	(If you answered YES) which kind of implants?		
3. Do you know people that have received a biomedical implant in their body?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
4. Are you familiar with the concept of biocompatibility?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
5. Are you familiar with the concept of bioresorbability?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
6. Do you know that certain materials dissolve in the human body in safe products?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
7. Do you know that the human body can safely dissolve an implant if suitable materials are used?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
8. Are your familiar with the concepts of nanotechnology or nanomaterials?			
YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER

Patient willingness to use the RESORB technology, once available

Concerning the possibility to receive a fully bioresorbable and implantable device to monitor anticancer drugs in future.			
1. I would like to have it			
AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
2. I will feel comfortable in having it, both emotionally and physically			
AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
3. I will feel confident in receiving it			
AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
4. I will feel safe about the full bioresorbability of the implant			
AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
5. It will help me to improve my health status			
AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
6. It will help my physicians to better monitor my health status			
AGREE	NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	DISAGREE	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER

Assessment of possible patient prejudices			
1) Do you think that a fully bioresorbable and implantable sensor for monitoring in real-time the levels of an anticancer drug in the body might be advantageous for patients?			
YES VERY MUCH	I DON'T KNOW	NOT AT ALL	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
2) Do you think that a fully bioresorbable and implantable sensor for monitoring in real-time the level of anticancer drugs in your body might make you feel better controlled than using traditional blood tests?			
YES VERY MUCH	I DON'T KNOW	NOT AT ALL	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
3) Would be worried about receiving a bioresorbable implant?			
YES VERY MUCH	I DON'T KNOW	NOT AT ALL	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
4) Do you think that such an implant would have some family, social, and economic consequences in your life?			
YES VERY MUCH	I DON'T KNOW	NOT AT ALL	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER
5) Do you think that anticancer drugs might have fewer side effects if the dosage is adjusted on the basis of the results coming from traditional blood test instead of a bioresorbable implant?			
YES VERY MUCH	I DON'T KNOW	NOT AT ALL	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER

6) Do you think that the bioresorbable implant would improve your life with respect to frequent hospital accesses?			
YES VERY MUCH	I DON'T KNOW	NOT AT ALL	PREFER NOT TO ANSWER

Please use this box for any comments or suggestions you wish to leave

We performed a statistical analysis of the answers we collected, which is reported here below.

Figure 1 shows the composition of the dataset, namely, the patient population we interviewed. The dataset mainly consists of woman (~65%) older than 45 years, the majority of which under anticancer therapy for at least 4 months.

Figure 1: Patient description. Statistical descriptors of the patients' population we interviewed

As to the awareness of the patients about implantable and bioresorbable technologies (Figure 2), the average trend indicates that dataset is split in half (Figure 2A) with ~50% of patients being unaware and the remaining 50% being mostly aware. Specifically, the patients seem to be aware about the existence of implantable devices while they are doubtful about the concept of biocompatibility and bioresorbability (Figure 2B). A certain level of uncertainty

(~70%) also emerges about the familiarity with the concept of nanotechnology and nanomaterials.

Figure 2: Patient awareness about implantable and bioresorbable technologies. A) Pie chart of the average trend regarding the patient awareness about bioresorbable implants and technologies. B) Pie charts with the percentage of the answers the patients provided to this section of the questionnaire.

As to the patient willingness to use the RESORB technology (Figure 3), a large percentage (~70%) of the patients are positive with the idea of receiving a bioresorbable sensor for monitoring the level of an anticancer drug in their body (Figure 3A). In particular, the patients not only would comfortably accept the RESORB technology, but they also believe that the proposed technology could help them and their physicians to monitor their health status (~70%).

Figure 3: Patient willingness to use the RESORB technology, once available. A) Pie chart showing the percentage of the patients that agree, disagree, or without any specific opinion about the usage/acceptance of a RESORB device into their body. B) Pie charts with the percentage of the answers the patients provided to this section of the questionnaire.

In order to understand what are the reasons why ~25% of patients have doubts about the RESORB technology, we can rely on specific questions we asked to determine possible prejudices about this technology. Results of this section of the questionnaire are shown in Figure 4. Overall, the majority of the patients have not a specific opinion about pro and cons of using a bioresorbable implant (Figure 4A) and the remaining patients do not have significant prejudices. In particular, a large percentage of the patients believe that they would be better controlled/treated with respect to frequent hospitalization, though some doubts still remain about the safety of the implant and social, economic, family impacts of the implant on the patient life.

Figure 4: Assessment of possible patient prejudices. A) Pie chart showing the average level of possible prejudices regarding the acceptance/usage of a RESORB sensor into the patients' body. B) Pie charts with the percentage of the answers the patients provided to this part of the questionnaire.

3.6 Participation to national/international conferences

National Conferences

Vandini E., Corsi M., Pagni A., Mariani S., Golinelli G., Debrassi A., Egri G., Leo G., Vilella A., Dähne L., Giuliani D., Barillaro G., "Biocompatibility study of bioresorbable nanostructured chemical sensor for monitoring of pH level in a mouse model", 42nd National SIF Conference, 13th-16th November 2024, Sorrento (Italy), poster

Corsi M., Barillaro G., "Implantable and bioresorbable sensors", ICOP 2024, 17th-19th June 2024, Florence (Italy), invited talk.

Corsi M., Pagni A., Mariani S., Golinelli G., Debrassi A., Egri G., Leo G., Vandini E., Vilella A., Dähne L., Giuliani D., Barillaro G., "Implantable and bioresorbable nanostructured fluorescence sensor for in-vivo pH monitoring", AISEM 2024, 7th-9th February 2024, Bologna (Italy), talk.

Corsi M., Pagni A., Mariani S., Golinelli G., Debrassi A., Egri G., Leo G., Vandini E., Vilella A., Dähne L., Giuliani D., Barillaro G., "Bioresorbable optical sensor for wireless and real-time vaginal pH monitoring", AISEM 2024, 7th-9th February 2024, Bologna (Italy), poster.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "A flexible vapor-phase synthesis method for producing MIP-based sensors", AISEM 2024, 7th-9th February 2024, Bologna (Italy), talk.

Di Giulio T., Gagliani F., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "Reconfigurable sensors for the optical detection of biomolecular targets by metal-ion interactions", AISEM 2024, 7th-9th February 2024, Bologna (Italy), poster.

Mazzotta E., Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., "Vapor-phase synthesis of molecularly imprinted polymers for optical sensing applications", GS 2023, December 2023, Rome (Italy), talk.

Di Giulio T., Mariani S., Corsi M., Malitesta C., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "Optical detection of human hemoglobin by a molecularly imprinted polymer prepared by a novel vapor-phase synthesis", LEbiotech 2023 workshop, 27th-29th September 2023, Lecce (Italy), talk.

Di Giulio T., Gagliani F., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "A versatile approach for achieving metal ion mediated interactions on porous silicon interferometers", SCI 2023, 17th-21st September 2023, Vasto (Italy), talk.

Mazzotta E., Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., "Molecular imprinting and sensing technology: a happy marriage based on established and innovative strategies", SCI 2023, 17th-21st September 2023, Vasto (Italy), talk.

Asif M.I., Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "A new molecularly imprinted polymer based optical sensor for label free detection of quercetin", SCI 2023, 17th-21st September 2023, Vasto (Italy), poster.

International Conferences

Corsi M., Pagi A., Mariani S., La Mattina A.A., Egri G., Dähne L., Barillaro G., “Flexible and bioresorbable optical sensor for wireless and real-time vaginal pH monitoring”, IFETC 2024, 15th-18th September 2024, Bologna (Italy), poster.

Djenizian T., “From stretchable Li-ion microbatteries to bioresorbable Na-ion batteries”, 4th CNRS-AMU-UTokyo Workshop, 14th-15th October 2024, Tokyo (Japan), invited speaker.

Barillaro G., “Implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo monitoring of clinical-diagnostic markers”, ECS PRIME 2024 Meeting, 10th October 2024, Honolulu, Hawaii (USA), invited talk

Djenizian T., “High performance flexible and stretchable wire Li-ion batteries”, Nanotextology 2024, 29th June-6th July 2024, Thessaloniki (Greece), invited speaker.

Vandini E., Corsi M., Paghi A., Mariani S., Golinelli G., Debrassi A., Egri G., Leo G., Vilella A., Dähne L., Giuliani D., Barillaro G., “In vivo study of bioresorbable nanostructured chemical sensor for monitoring of pH level”, Nanotextology 2024, 29th June-6th July 2024, Thessaloniki (Greece), talk.

Di Giulio T., Giancane G., De Gennaro M., Barca A., Verri T., Mazzotta E., Malitesta C., “Electrosynthesis of a molecularly imprinted poly(metalloporphyrin) for the selective detection of carnosine”, ESEAC 2024, 23rd-26th June 2024, Ulm (Germany), poster.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Gonzato C., Haupt K., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “Photo-iniferter polymerization: a convenient approach for integrating molecularly imprinted polymers with nanostructured sensors”, MIP 2024, 19th-21st June 2024, Verona (Italy), talk.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “A versatile vapor-phase polymerization approach for molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) in optical sensing”, MIP 2024, 19th-21st June 2024, Verona (Italy), poster.

Gagliani F., Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., Barca A., Verri T., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “An innovative and versatile reconfigurable sensor for biomolecules detection via metal-ion mediated recognition”, IECB 2024, 20th-22nd May 2024, online, talk.

Asif I.M., Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “An innovative vapor-phase synthesis approach to obtain MIP-based optical sensors for label free detection of quercetin”, IECB 2024, 20th-22nd May 2024, online, poster.

Corsi M., Paghi A., Mariani S., Golinelli G., Debrassi A., Egri G., Leo G., Vandini E., Vilella A., Dähne L., Giuliani D., Barillaro G., “Bioresorbable optical sensor for wireless and real-

time vaginal pH monitoring”, PSST Conference 2024, 28th April-2nd May 2024, Brno (Czech Republic), poster.

Corsi M., Paghi A., Mariani S., Golinelli G., Debrassi A., Egri G., Leo G., Vandini E., Vilella A., Dähne L., Giuliani D., Barillaro G., “Implantable and bioresorbable nanopstructured fluorescence sensor for in-vivo pH monitoring”, PSST Conference 2024, 28th April-2nd May 2024, Brno (Czech Republic), talk.

Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Mariani S., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “Vapor-phase synthesis of molecularly imprinted polymers on nanostructured materials at room-temperature”, PSST Conference 2024, 28th April-2nd May 2024, Brno (Czech Republic), poster.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Gonzato C., Haupt K., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “A new versatile photo-iniferter polymerization approach to obtain molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) on nanostructured porous silicon (PSi) interferometers”, PSST Conference 2024, 28th April-2nd May 2024, Brno (Czech Republic), poster.

Barillaro G., “Implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo monitoring of clinical-diagnostic markers”, IEEE Sensors, 30th October 2023, Vienna (Austria). Invited talk.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “An innovative and versatile vapor-phase synthesis approach to obtain MIP-based sensors”, Eurosensors XXXV Conference 2023, 10th – 13th September 2023, Lecce (Italy), poster.

Di Giulio T., Gagliani F., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “A flexible functionalization strategy of porous siliconinterferometers for chemical sensing application”, Eurosensors XXXV Conference 2023, 10th – 13th September 2023, Lecce (Italy), poster.

Barillaro G., “Implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo real time tracking of analytes of clinical interest”, 243rd ElectroChemical Society (ECS) Meeting, 30th May 2023, Boston (USA), invited talk.

Barillaro G., “Implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo tracking of clinical/diagnostic markers”, Nanospain 2023, 26th April 2023, Tarragona (Spain), keynote presentation.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Gonzato C., Haupt K., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “Molecularly imprinted polymers by photo-iniferter polymerization: an easy way of functionalizing nanostructured porous silicon”, Biosensors 2023, 5th-8th June 2023, Busan (South Korea), poster.

E. Mazzotta, Di Giulio T., Malitesta C., Corsi M., Mariani S., Barillaro G., "MIP room-temperature vapor-phase deposition: an easy flexible strategy for MIP deposition on nanostructured surfaces for sensing applications", Biosensors 2023, 5th-8th June 2023, Busan (South Korea), poster.

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Malitesta C., Gonzato C., Haupt K., Corsi M., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "A photo-initiated polymerization for molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) synthesis on porous silicon (Psi) interferometers for chemical sensing", IECB 2023, 8th-21st May 2023, online, poster.

Corsi, M., Paghi, A., Mariani, S., Golinelli, G., Debrassi, A., Egri, G., Leo, G., Vandini, E., Vilella, A., Dähne, L., Giuliani, D., Barillaro, G., "*Implantable and Bioresorbable Nanostructured Fluorescence Sensor for In Vivo Ph Monitoring*", 2022 IEEE SENSORS, 30th October-2nd November 2022, Dallas (US).

Seminars and Lectures

Barillaro G., "Layer-by-Layer Self-Assembly of Polyelectrolytes: From Ultrathin Ambipolar Capacitors to Wearable Label-Free Biosensors". Seminar at the COST Action 2016 NETPORE Meeting, 2nd October 2024, Ljubljana (Slovenia).

Barillaro G., "Human monitoring – New Approaches to Sensors Fabrication and Design". Lecture at the 1st ForeLab Summer School, 11th September 2024, Pisa (Italy).

Djenizian T., "Fabrication and modification of TiO₂ nanotubes for high performance Li-ion micro batteries". Lecture at the 3rd Summer NetPore Training School, 8th-12th July 2024, Ankara (Turkey).

Barillaro G., "Layer-by-Layer Self-Assembly of Polyelectrolytes: From Ultrathin Ambipolar Capacitors to Wearable Label-Free Biosensors". Seminar at the National Centre for Scientific Research Demokritos, 9th July 2024, Athens (Greece).

Morgado J., "materials in Medicine". Seminar at the University of Lisbon, April 2024, Lisbon (Portugal).

Morgado J., "Electrical stimulation of neural stem cells: materials and setup". Seminar at the University of Auckland, February 2024, Auckland (New Zealand).

Barillaro G., "Implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo diagnostics". Seminar at the COST Action 2016 NETPORE Winter School, 26th February 2024, Turin (Italy).

Barillaro G., "Implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo monitoring of clinical-diagnostic markers". Lecture at the Queen's Mary University, 7th February 2024, London (UK).

Barillaro G., Seminar on RESORB's implantable and bioresorbable chemical sensors for in-vivo monitoring of clinical-diagnostic markers, CEISAM institute of Nantes, 29th January 2024, Nantes (France).

Giuliani D., "Precise medicine in chemotherapy". Lecture at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. November 2023, Modena (Italy).

Barillaro G., "Ex-vivo and in-vivo optical sensing with porous silicon". Seminars at the University of California San Diego, 24th July and 4th August 2023, San Diego (USA).

Barillaro G., Seminar on RESORB project, University of California Los Angeles, 17th July 2023, Los Angeles (USA).

Barillaro G., Seminar on RESORB Project and results on implantable and bioresorbable porous silicon sensors, National Centre for Scientific Research Demokritos, 3rd June 2023, Athens (Greece).

3.7 Press and Web News Release

RESORB "stories" are available at the UNIPi's news pages (UnipiNews) and web release:

<https://www.unipi.it/index.php/component/k2/item/23833-un-sensore-biorassorbibile-sottopelle-puo-monitorare-i-segnali-del-corpo?Itemid=637>; 23rd June 2022: "Un sensore biorassorbibile sottopelle può monitorare i segnali del corpo" (English translation: A bioresorbable sensor implanted under the skin to monitor body signals);

<https://www.unipi.it/index.php/component/k2/item/22464-finanziato-resorb-il-primo-progetto-del-nuovo-programma-europeo-horizon-europe?Itemid=637>; 19th November 2021: "Finanziato RESORB, il primo progetto del nuovo programma europeo Horizon Europe" (English translation: the new European Horizon Europe program has funded RESORB);

https://www.repubblica.it/salute/2022/08/03/news/sensore_sottopelle_effetto_farmac_i-360056468/; 3rd August 2022: "E con un sensore sottopelle sapremo se i farmaci fanno effetto" (English translation: A sensor under the skin will finally tell us whenever drugs are effective);

<https://medicoepaziente.it/2022/biosensori-impiantabili-la-nuova-frontiera-della-diagnostica/>; 6th August 2022; "Biosensori impiantabili. La nuova frontiera della diagnostica" (English translation: Implantable biosensors: the new frontier in diagnostics).

3.8 Participation to popular science events

In order to raise awareness of the RESORB technology and gain social acceptance, we participated and/or planned to participate to the following popular science events:

Bright Night, the EU Research Nigh 2022 and 2023.

Author(s)	Title	Location Date	Audience Size
G. Barillaro (UNIFI)	Nanosensori biodegradabili: come potrebbe cambiare il monitoraggio di cibo, ambiente e salute (oral presentation) (English translation: Biodegradable nanosensors: how they would impact the monitoring of food, environment and health)	Pisa 30.09.2022	40
E. Mazzotta (UNISAL)	Biomimetic receptors in bioresorbable sensors (poster presentation)	Lecce 30.09.2022	40
G. Barillaro (UNIFI)	Sensori biorisorbibili nel corpo: nuove frontiere della medicina (oral presentation) (English translation: Biodegradable Implantable bioresorbable sensors: new frontiers in nanomedicine)	Pisa 29.09.2023	45

3.9 Papers on International Journals

RESORB has seven gold open-access publications:

Corsi M., Maurina E., Surdo S., Vandini E., Daini E., Vilella A., Leo G., Farshchian M., Grisendi G., Golinelli G., Dominici M, Bocci G., Giuliani D., and Barillaro G., “*In-vivo* and *in-situ* monitoring of doxorubicin pharmacokinetics with an implantable bioresorbable optical sensor” *Science Advances* 2025 (DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.ads0265)

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Corsi M., Rajpal S., Mizaikoff B., Ditaranto N., De Benedetto G.E., Malitesta C., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., “A Molecularly Imprinted Polymer-Based Porous Silicon Optical Sensor for Quercetin Detection in Wines”, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2025 (DOI: 10.1021/acsami.4c21238); <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acsami.4c21238>

Di Giulio T., Asif I.M., Corsi M., De Benedetto G.E., Malitesta C., Haupt K., Barillaro G., Gonzato C., Mazzotta E., "Visible-Light Photo-Iniferter Polymerization of Molecularly Imprinted Polymers for Direct Integration with Nanotransducers", *Small Methods* 2025, 2401315 (DOI: 10.1002/smt.202401315); <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/smt.202401315>

Muniraj V.K.A, Vijayan B. L., Hammoud H., Delattre R., Ramuz M., Djenizian E., Vandini E., Giuliani D., Djenizian T., "Bioresorbable and Wireless Rechargeable Implanted Na-ion Battery for Temporary Medical Devices", *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2025, 2417353 (DOI: 10.1002/adfm.202417353); <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/adfm.202417353?af=R>

Di Giulio T., Corsi M., Gagliani F., De Benedetto G., Malitesta C., Mazzei A., Barca A., Verri T., Barillaro G., Mazzotta E., "Reconfigurable Optical Sensor for Metal-Ion Mediated Label-Free Recognition of Different Biomolecular Targets", *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2024, 16, 33, 43752-43761(DOI:10.1021/acsami.4c08860); <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsami.4c08860>

Mazzotta E., Di Giulio T., Mariani S., Corsi M., Malitesta C., Barillaro G., "Vapor Phase Synthesis of Molecularly Imprinted Polymers in Nanostructured Porous Silicon for Selective and Sensitive Detection of Proteins", *Small* 2023, 2302274(DOI:10.1002/smll.202302274); <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/smll.202302274>

Paghi A.*, Corsi M.*, Mariani S., La Mattina A.A., Egri G., Dähne L., Barillaro G., "Wireless and Flexible Optoelectronic System for In-Situ Monitoring of Vaginal pH Using a Bioresorbable Fluorescence Sensor", *Adv. Mater. Technol.* 2023, 2201600 (DOI: 10.1002/admt.202201600); <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/admt.202201600>
*co-first authors

Corsi, M., Paghi, A., Mariani, S., Golinelli, G., Debrassi, A., Egri, G., Leo, G., Vandini, E., Vilella, A., Dähne, L., Giuliani, D., Barillaro, "Bioresorbable Nanostructured Chemical Sensor for Monitoring of pH Level In Vivo", *Adv. Sci.* 2022, 2202062 (DOI: 10.1002/advs.202202062); <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/advs.202202062>

3.10 Patents

Barillaro G., Surdo S., Minopoli A., Bellotti E., "Method for producing a bioresorbable and/or compatible optical fiber". European patent #EP24209472.2 deposited on October 29th, 2024.

Djenizian T., Vedikujilazhagan M., Hammoud H., Vijayan B.L., Delattre R., Ramuz M., "A Na-ion bioeliminable electrochemical accumulator comprising electrode pellets coated by a current collector thin film, associated manufacturing process and wireless recharging solution". European patent #EP24306269.2 deposited on July 26th, 2024.

Barillaro G., Corsi M., Maurina E., “Dispositivo di rilevazione della concentrazione di un farmaco” (English translation: Drug concentration detecting device). Italian patent P1215IT00 deposited on April 15th, 2024.

Djenizian T., Bhatia A., Baddour-Hadjean R., Pereira-Ramos J.P., Vijayan B.L., “A Na-ion bioresorbable and flexible electrochemical accumulator”. Application # EP23170468.5, filed 27 April 2023

3.11 Collaborations with industries

The RESORB technology has attracted the attention of “ab medica,” a company that operates in the biomedical sector by offering appropriate, inclusive, and sustainable patient care through the integration of clinical pathways with the best techniques and technologies available. Precisely, UNIFI and ab medica are collaborating for the development of a wireless, flexible device that will read data recorded by the RESORB optical sensors once implanted in the body and make them available to patients and doctors through a mobile app. Additionally, our the RESORB consortium and ab medica have been actively preparing two EU projects—one EIC Transition project that leverages the results of RESORB on the pH sensor, and one EIC Pathfinder Open project. These initiatives not only complement our current collaboration but also underscore our commitment to advancing cutting-edge biomedical technologies and fostering sustainable healthcare solutions.

4. BIBLIOGRAPHY/REFERENCES

1. RESORB Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan